

Title: Proof of Discovery Hash

SHA-256 Hash: e5fdfcce13b88c97d7ea76fc82e474b74e98da33bd9486061bbb992c4f5b94bf

Date generated: August 23, 2025

Description: This file contains the cryptographic hash of an unpublished discovery document. It serves as proof of authorship and prior existence, timestamped via Zenodo.